

IOT BASED GAS LEAKAGE DETECTION USING ARDUINO

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Abstract— This paper presents a novel method for detecting LPG leakage using a microcontroller-based Arduino. It aims to prevent accidents caused by LPG leakage by implementing safety measures. To detect the discharge, an Arduino-based LPG gas detector alarm can be developed. The paper uses the LPG detector MQ6 to acquire the signal intensity and an efficient Arduino-based signal processing mechanism to quantify the electrical signal accurately. The intensity of the LPG leakage is then classified into three categories: LOW, MEDIUM, and HIGH. The paper also displays the ratio and temperature on an alphanumeric display. The significance of this paper lies in its contribution to improving safety in domestic life by providing an important precautionary measure against LPG leakage.

Keywords— IOT, Arduino, LPG, MQ2 Gas Sensor, Buzzer;

I. INTRODUCTION

Liquefied petroleum gas, also known as LPG, is a non-renewable energy source that is produced from fossil fuels like gas and oil. Hydrocarbons with three or four carbon atoms, such propane (C₃H₈) and butane (C₄H₁₀), make up the majority of its constituents. Small concentrations of additional hydrocarbons might also be present, depending on the source and production process. LPG may also contain additional non-hydrocarbon compounds. Due to its extreme flammability, LPG should be kept in a well-ventilated area, away from potential ignition sources, to guarantee that any spills can be properly dispersed. Because LPG vapours are heavier than air, care must be taken during storage to prevent leaks from building up in low-lying areas. LPG has no fragrance in its natural condition, however it does have a distinct odour when appended to it prior to it leaving the primary storage terminals to help discover leaks. Ethyl mercaptan, a substance, is the source of this Odour.

The usage of petrol, especially LPG, in residential and commercial settings might provide serious safety issues. Gas leaks can have detrimental effects on both human life and property. A project has been started to develop an inspection system that can identify LPG gas leaks and take the necessary safety precautions in real-time in order to address this issue. The device uses sensors to identify gas leaks and activates a buzzer as a warning signal right away. Another article examines the characteristics of LPG, its make-up, and any possible risks related to its use. The implementation of a gas

leak detecting system is the paper's main concern appended to it prior to it leaving the primary storage terminals to help discover leaks. The source of this odour is a chemical known as ethyl merc, which is detected by MQ-6 gas sensors and DHT11 temperature sensors. The technology is made to identify gas leaks and categorize them into three levels of concentration, enabling quick response to stop any additional damage. The technology also notifies affected parties via email and text message, enhancing the overall safety of gas infrastructure.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In May 2020, Dr.Chetana Tukkoji's article "LPG Gas Leakage Detection Using IoT" was published in the International Journal of Engineering, Applied Sciences, and Technology. The design and deployment of an IoT-based LPG gas leak detection system are covered in the paper. The system monitors for gas leaks and alerts users via a smartphone app or other electronic means using gas sensors, microcontrollers, and wireless communication. The page gives a thorough explanation of the system's hardware and software components, as well as its implementation and testing. The prospective uses and advantages of the LPG gas leakage detection system are also covered by the author, including enhanced safety and diminished hazards from gas leaks. [1]. In 2020, Syeda Bushra Shahewaz published "Gas Leakage Detection and Alerting System using Arduino Uno" in the Global Journal of Engineering and Technology Advances. The creation of a gas leak detection and warning system utilising an Arduino Uno microcontroller is discussed in the article. The system uses gas sensors to identify the presence of gas and then notifies the user of any potential dangers via a buzzer and an LED. The system's implementation and testing, as well as the hardware and software components used in the system, are all thoroughly explained by the author. It has been demonstrated that the system is efficient in finding gas leaks and sending out prompt alerts to stop any potentially dangerous situations. [2].

Juhi Chaudhary wrote the piece titled "Detection of Gas Leakage and Automatic Alert," which was posted in January 2019 on the SSRN Electronic Journal. The creation of a gas leakage detection and alert system that may be utilised in

households, workplaces and industries is discussed in the article. The technology is made to find gas leaks and notify users right away to stop any accidents or dangerous situations. The system's technique, which makes use of gas sensors, microcontrollers, and wireless communication modules, is described by the authors. The microcontroller analyses the data and uses wireless communication modules to send notifications to the user's mobile device when the gas sensors have detected the presence of gas. [3]. A gas sensor module and an Arduino board are used by the system to process sensor data and sound an alert in the event of a gas leak. Additionally, the system has a GSM module that, in the event of a gas leak, sends an SMS alert to the user's mobile phone. The gas sensor, Arduino board, and GSM module, among other hardware and software parts of the system, have all been described in great depth by the authors. They have also talked about the sensitivity and precision of the gas sensor as well as testing and validating the device. [4].

The article "Early Detection of Leaks on Gas Cylinders Using Arduino Based MQ-6 Sensors" describes a system for detecting gas leaks from cylinders using MQ-6 gas sensors and an Arduino microcontroller. The authors describe the hardware and software design of the system, as well as its testing and evaluation. The results show that the system is capable of detecting gas leaks at an early stage and can provide a timely warning to prevent any potential hazards. The article provides useful insights into the development of gas leak detection systems using low-cost sensors and microcontrollers. However, the study has limitations, such as the lack of a detailed comparison with other similar systems and the limited scope of the testing. Nonetheless, the article can serve as a useful reference for researchers and practitioners working on gas leak detection systems using Arduino-based sensors.[5]. The design and implementation of a smart LPG gas monitoring and automatic booking system with an alarm system using the Internet of Things are presented in this paper. An LPG gas sensor, an Arduino Uno board, an ESP8266 Wi-Fi module, and a mobile application make up the suggested system. The Arduino Uno board processes the data and controls the device after the LPG gas sensor detects the gas level. The findings demonstrated the system's ability to accurately monitor gas levels, automatically order gas, and detect gas leaks and immediately provide notifications.[6].

The paper presents an Internet of Things (IoT) based hazardous gas leakage detection system using Arduino UNO. The system consists of MQ-135 gas sensor, Arduino UNO board, ESP8266 Wi-Fi module, and a buzzer. The MQ-135 gas sensor detects the hazardous gas leakage and sends the signal to the Arduino UNO board, which is connected to the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module. The Wi-Fi module sends an alert message to the user's smartphone using IoT technology. The system was tested with hazardous gases, and the results showed that it was able to detect the gas leakage accurately and send alerts in real-time. The paper provides a detailed description of the system's hardware and software components and presents the experimental results.[7]. The paper describes the design and implementation of an Arduino-based gas leakage detection system using IoT. The system comprises an MQ-6 gas sensor, an Arduino Uno

board, an ESP8266 Wi-Fi module, and a buzzer. The MQ-6 sensor detects the gas leakage and sends the signal to the Arduino Uno board, which is connected to the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module. The Wi-Fi module sends an alert message to the user's smartphone using IoT technology. The paper presents a detailed description of the hardware and software components of the system and the experimental results. The system was tested with LPG gas, and the results demonstrated its capability to detect gas leakage accurately and send alerts in real-time.[8]. The design and deployment of an Internet of Things-based system for gas leak detection and prevention are discussed in the study. The system use an ESP8266 Wi-Fi module to transmit the data to the cloud after using a MQ-5 gas sensor to identify the gas leak. Using IoT technology, the cloud server sends an alert message to the user's smartphone and stores the data. The system also contains a preventative feature that, in the event that a gas leak is discovered, shuts off the gas supply. The paper offers the experimental findings as well as a thorough explanation of the system's hardware and software components. The outcomes demonstrate that the system was able to precisely identify the gas leak and avert any dangers.[9].

The paper presents the design and implementation of an Internet of Things (IoT) based gas monitoring system using Arduino. The system uses an MQ-6 gas sensor to detect the gas leakage, and the data is transmitted to the cloud server through the Wi-Fi module. The user can access the gas concentration data in real-time using a mobile application. The paper provides a detailed description of the system's hardware and software components and presents the experimental results. The experimental results show that the system is able to detect gas leakage accurately and provide real-time monitoring.[10]. The paper titled "IoT Application for Gas Leakages Monitoring" by Ba Thanh Nguyen and Anh Vu Nguyen, published in the International Research Journal of Advanced Engineering and Science, discusses the implementation of an Internet of Things (IoT) application for gas leakage monitoring. The proposed system includes an MQ-2 gas sensor, an Arduino board, and a Wi-Fi module. The gas sensor detects the gas leakage, and the Arduino board processes the signal and sends the data to the cloud server via the Wi-Fi module. The cloud server stores and analyzes the data and sends an alert message to the user's smartphone in case of gas leakage. The authors tested the system with various gases, and the results showed that it was able to detect the gas leakage accurately and send real-time alerts to the user's smartphone. The paper provides a useful contribution to the field of gas leakage monitoring using IoT technology.[11].

The Internet of Things (IoT) technology is used in the article "IoT Gas Leakage Detector and Warning Generator" to demonstrate a gas leak detection system. The system has a microprocessor, a Wi-Fi module, and a gas sensor that allows data to be transmitted to a cloud server. The authors suggest a brand-new algorithm for spotting gas leaks that takes the properties of gas molecules and the surrounding temperature into account. The system has the ability to make an alarm sound, activate the exhaust fan, and send warning messages to the user's smartphone via an application. The performance of the system, including accuracy, response time, and power

consumption, are also evaluated by the authors through trials.[12]. The article "IoT Based Gas Leakage Detection and Alarming System using Blynk platforms" introduces a system for spotting and notifying gas leaks using the Blynk platform. The authors are from the Al-Mansour University College's Computer Technology Engineering Department in Baghdad, Iraq. In June 2022, the article appeared in volume 18, issue 1 of the Iraqi Journal for Electrical and Electronic Engineering. A thorough explanation of the system design, including its hardware and software components, is given in the article. The system was created by the authors using an Arduino, a MQ-5 gas sensor, a Wi-Fi module, and the Blynk platform. The Wi-Fi module links the system to the internet while the MQ-5 gas sensor monitors for gas leaks. Developers utilise the Blynk platform to create a user interface and to inform users via their smartphones in the event of a gas leak. The system was put to the test with various gas concentrations, and the authors then presented their findings. The findings demonstrated that the system can effectively identify gas leaks and promptly notify the user. The article also addresses the system's benefits and drawbacks and suggests more research to enhance the system's functionality.[13].

III. METHODOLOGY

LPG Gas is crucial, While LPG is a valuable desire for every social unit, a leak could be disastrous. There are several products that detect the leak in order to notify of it and prevent any mishaps. Here, we present an LPG gas detector alarm built on an Arduino platform. If a gas leak occurs, this method finds it and alerts the user with a buzz from a buzzer that is connected to the circuit.

Figure 1:

Block Diagram of gas leakage detecting and alerting system

Source: <https://www.mdpi.com/2673-4591/2/1/28>

Hardware and software requirements

The gas leakage detection system using Arduino works by detecting the presence of gas in the environment using the gas sensor module. The Arduino board receives the signal from the gas sensor module and activates the buzzer to sound an alarm. The LCD can be used to display relevant information

such as gas concentration levels. The transistor acts as a switch to control the buzzer, and the resistor limits the flow of current to the gas sensor module. The hardware components are connected to the Arduino board using the breadboard and connecting wires. The software components, including the Arduino IDE and libraries, are used to program and interface with the Arduino board.

Hardware Requirments :

1. Arduino UNO:

In Figure 2, an Arduino UNO microcontroller is used. The Arduino board serves as the system's main processing unit, and all of the components are connected to it outside and configured to run in unison. It is an electronic prototyping board that supports the 8-bit, 16 MHz Atmega-328. During this time, serial communication is enabled, and there are 6 analogue input pins and 14 digital input/output pins, 6 of which are PWM. It runs on 5 volts. Each pin can be used to regulate a certain function.

Non-volatile storage and EEPROM make up the storage. The unmistakable distinction between a non-volatile storage and an EEPROM is that the non-volatile storage's contents are erasable. Unlike an EEPROM, the entire gadget is where one can judge on the basis of bytes and sections and erase. The availability of non-volatile memory, where an EEPROM byte has a no-erasing option, during which the blocks of the contents are divided and subsequently erased one block at a time. because the non-volatile storage was really programmed when it was plugged into the system board socket. The PCB's recent improvement, the BIOSROM, is widely utilized.

Figure-2:
 Arduino software system
 Source:

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Arduino>

Pin No	Function	Name
1	Ground (0V)	Ground
2	Serial data output pin	Data
3	Linear output pin; not connected	NC
4	Supply voltage; 5V	VCC
5	Supply voltage; 5V	VCC
6	Ground (0V)	Ground
7	Ground (0V)	Ground
8	Antenna input pin	ANT

Table-1. Pin Specification

Source: <https://www.engineersgarage.com/arduino-based-gas-leakage-detection-using-mq6-gas-sensor/>

2. Mq6 Gas Sensor :

Experts have provided explanations of the various LPG architecture components on YouTube. According to label sensitivity, the sensing element has the ability to detect a variety of flammable gas types. The potentiometer that is installed within the jailbreak board of the MQ6 gas sensing element may be used to name this sensing component. The sensor device produces a little amount of analogue data. The MQ-6 can detect gas concentrations anywhere between 200 and 10,000 ppm. Analogue resistance to a certain degree is the sensor's output. One i/o pin from the host microcontroller is required for interface with the sensing element module, which is finished by a 4-pin board compatible Stp header. Once powered on, the onboard microcontroller starts the initial heating cycle and activates the LPG sensing element output. It discovered the LPG concentration at low frequency. If the value is higher than the present value, it will alert the host controller by pulling the output pin to high and beginning to blink the onboard diode. The sensor element module is specifically designed to create a way of examining LPG supply and to line an alarm limit when the source becomes excessive [10]. It has four pins, and Table 1's description of the LPG Gas Sensor provides more information.

Pin No	Function	Name
1	Ground (0V)	Ground
2	Serial data input pin	Data
3	Supply voltage; 5V	VCC
4	Antenna output pin	ANT

Table-2. Pin Specification

Source: <https://www.engineersgarage.com/arduino-based-gas-leakage-detection-using-mq6-gas-sensor/>

Figure-3:

MQ6 GAS SENSOR

Source: <https://www.indiamart.com/proddetail/mq6-gas-sensor-23408045712.html>

3. Jumper Wire:

A jumper wire is an electrical wire, or group of wires within a cable, with a connector or pin at each end (or typically without them - merely "tinned"), that is frequently used to connect the internal or external components of a board or different model or test circuit without fastening. Individual jump wires are installed by fitting their "end connectors" into the slots made available by a board, a printed circuit board's header connector, or a piece of equipment.

Figure-4:

Jumper Wire

Source: <https://sumeetinstrument.com/Jumper-Wire-Male-to-Female-40pc-Set-20cm>

4. BUZZER (Piezo Electric)

A buzzer or pager is an auditory signalling device, which can be powered by electricity (Piezo, for short), a mechanical device, or both. It contains two pins. Its simple design and inexpensive cost make it suitable for use in a variety of applications, including computers, decision bells, and car/truck reversing indicators [13]. It is also true that the phenomenon of certain materials producing electricity when mechanical pressure is applied to them also occurs the opposite way around. There are two types of piezoelectric materials: natural and man-made. Piezo ceramic is a type of man-made material that has an electrical impact on piezo waves and is frequently used to generate the disc at the centre of piezo buzzers.

Figure-5:

BUZZER (Piezo Electric)

Source:

<https://quartzcomponents.com/products/piezo-buzzer>

5. LED Lights :

The red LED will indicate a gas leakage, while the green LED will indicate that there is no gas leakage.

Figure-6:

LED Lights(Green & Red)

6. USB Cable

USB cable is used to connect an Arduino board to a computer or other device for programming and power. The USB cable connects to the USB port on the Arduino board and the USB port on the computer or other device.

Figure-7:

USB Cable

Source: <https://floricx.in/store/arduino-cable-type-a-to-mini-b/>

Software requirements:

1. Arduino IDE

The open-source software platform known as Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment) is used to write code for Arduino boards. The Arduino open-source electronics platform lets users build interactive projects, electrical prototypes, and other gadgets using simple hardware and software. To write, compile, and upload code to an Arduino board, use the IDE's user-friendly interface.

The Java-based Arduino IDE can be used with Windows, Mac OS X, and Linux operating systems. It has a bootloader that enables you to upload your code to an Arduino board, a code editor, a serial monitor, a compiler, and other tools. You can use the IDE's extensive library of pre-written code, known as sketches, to start your projects. The simplicity of the Arduino IDE is one of its benefits. Even novices who are unfamiliar with electronics and programming will find it simple to operate. Additionally, the IDE supports a wide range of programming languages, allowing programmers to write code in their preferred language, such as C, C++, and Python.

The Arduino IDE is a strong tool for creating projects using Arduino boards overall. It is a popular option for professionals, students, and amateurs alike because to its user-friendly design and support for numerous programming languages.

[2]IV. METHOD OF IMPLEMENTATION

IoT based gas leakage detection using Arduino with buzzer is an advanced method of detecting gas leakage in a more efficient and convenient way. This system combines the power of IoT with the simplicity and ease of use of Arduino to create a smart gas leakage detection system. In this system, the gas sensor module is connected to the Arduino board, which is then connected to the internet via a WiFi module or Ethernet shield. The system can then send real-time gas leakage alerts to a user's smartphone or email address, allowing for quick and effective action to be taken. The buzzer is used to provide an audible alert in case of gas leakage detection. This system is highly scalable and can be used in a variety of settings, including homes, industries, and public places.

The creation of a gas detection system will take three steps:

1. Connect all the equipment.
2. Codify and upload it to the Arduino board.
3. Test the system we developed.

1. **Connect all the equipment.**

- Let's first pair the Arduino with the MQ-6 gas sensor.
- As a result, you must connect the Arduino's 5 volts pin to the VCC pin of the gas sensor.
- Next, connect the GND pin of the gas sensor to the Arduino's GND pin.
- Connect the analog-0 pin of the Arduino to the OUT/A0 pin of the MQ-6 gas sensor.
- The 162 LCD should now be connected to the Arduino's digital pins as shown in the diagram.

- You can refer to our post on integrating an Arduino with a 16x2 LCD display for further information.
- Connect the Arduino's digital-pin to the positive leg of the green LED after that.
- Connect the red LED's positive leg to the Arduino's digital pin.
- Finally, use a 220 ohm resistor to connect the negative legs of both LEDs to the Arduino's GND pin.
- Here, a resistor is being used to prevent LEDs from fusing. Now that your circuit is finished, you can move on to the following action.

2. Codify and upload it to the Arduino board.

The LiquidCrystal.h library needs to be installed in your Arduino IDE first.

```
sketch_mar29a | Arduino 1.8.19
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
sketch_mar29a
int red_led=13;//indicates gas
int green_led=12;//indicates normal
int smokeA0 = A0;//indicates sensor is connected to A5
int sensorThres=50;
int buzzer = 11;//The threshold value

void setup()
{
  pinMode(red_led,OUTPUT);//red led as output
  pinMode(green_led,OUTPUT);//green led as output
  pinMode(A0,INPUT);//sensor as input
  pinMode(buzzer, OUTPUT);
  Serial.begin(9600);//starts the code
}
void loop()//loops
{
  int gas_avalue=analogRead(smokeA0);//reads sensor value
  if (gas_avalue > sensorThres)//sees if it reached threshold value
  {
    digitalWrite(red_led, HIGH);//turns on red led
    digitalWrite(red_led, HIGH);
    digitalWrite(buzzer, HIGH); // turn on buzzer
    digitalWrite(green_led, LOW);//turns off green led
  }
  else//if it hasn't reached threshold value
  {
    digitalWrite(red_led, LOW);//turns red led off
  }
  delay(100);//delay 0.1 sec
}
```

Code:

```
int red_led=13;//indicates gas
int green_led=12;//indicates normal
int smokeA0 = A0;//indicates sensor is connected
to A5
int sensorThres=50;
int buzzer = 11;//The threshold value
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```
void setup()
{
  pinMode(red_led,OUTPUT);//red led as output
  pinMode(green_led,OUTPUT);//green led as
output
  pinMode(A0,INPUT);//sensor as input
  pinMode(buzzer, OUTPUT);
  Serial.begin(9600);//starts the code
}
void loop()//loops
{
  int gas_avalue=analogRead(smokeA0);//reads
sensor value
  if (gas_avalue > sensorThres)//sees if it reached
threshold value
  {
    digitalWrite(red_led, HIGH);//turns on red led
    digitalWrite(red_led, HIGH);
    digitalWrite(buzzer, HIGH); // turn on buzzer
    digitalWrite(green_led, LOW);//turns off green
led
  }
  else//if it hasn't reached threshold value
  {
    digitalWrite(red_led, LOW);//turns red led off
    digitalWrite(buzzer, LOW);
    digitalWrite(green_led, HIGH);//turn green led
on
  }
  delay(100);//delay 0.1 sec
}
```

[3] V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

[4] By applying a little amount of LPG gas close to the sensor, this model has been tested. A signal is then sent to the microcontroller once the MQ-6 gas sensor recognises the LPG gas. The microcontroller then transmits an active signal to other distantly related devices. Thus, a buzzer is heard. With the aid of a solenoid valve, the gas supply is cut off simultaneously. When the reset button is pressed, the model returns to its ready state for gas detection. The proposed gas leakage detector performed admirably and produced accurate execution results during the testing period. After numerous observations of the results, the outcome was generally consistent. It could take the Gas Sensor a few seconds to recognise the gas escape, but as soon as it is detected, the valve is promptly closed.

1. The Arduino is on. The Green Light is on

2. The Red light is on, The gas leakage is detected

3. The Red Light and Buzzer is on in the gas leakage detected.

[5] VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, utilizing an Arduino to detect gas leaks is a cost-efficient and reliable technique to find leaks and avert

potentially harmful circumstances. To track the level of gas concentration in a space or environment, this system connects a gas sensor module to an Arduino board. The technology sets off an alarm and sends out a warning when the gas concentration surpasses a predetermined level. Systems for detecting gas leaks based on Arduino are highly adaptable and may be customized for various situations and gas types. They are perfect for usage in homes, businesses, and public spaces because they are very simple to install and utilize. Overall, using an Arduino to detect gas leaks is an effective, reasonably priced, and trustworthy solution to stop leaks and guarantee the security of people and property.

[6] VII. FUTURE WORK

The system can be connected to the internet and deliver real time gas concentration values to the user's smartphone or computer with the inclusion of IoT capabilities.

VIII. REFERENCES

- [7] Dr.Chetana Tukkoji, Mr. Sanjeev Kumar A. N Assistant Professor, Dept. of CSE Assistant Professor, Dept. of CSE GITAM School of Technology, Bengaluru . Article . May 2020 DOI: 10.33564/IJEAST.2020.v04i12.108.
- [8] Shreya Bushra Shahewaz, PG Student, Department of Master of Computer Applications, School of CS & IT, Jain (Deemed-to-be-University).
- [9] Juhi Chaudhary, *Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, Detection of Gas Leakage and Automatic Alert* January 2019, *SSRN Electronic Journal*, DOI:10-2139/ssrn-3350271.
- [10] *Anurag Mishra*, <https://www.researchgate.net/institution/Krishna-Institute-Of-Engineering-And-Technology> *Detection of Gas Leakage and Automatic Alert* January 2019, *SSRN Electronic Journal*, DOI:10-2139/ssrn-3350271.
- [11] Early Detection of Leaks on Gas Cylinders Using Arduino Based MQ-6 Sensors To cite this article: E Fatkiyah et al 2019 J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 1413 012030.
- [12] International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET) e-ISSN: 2395-0056 Volume: 08 Issue: 06 | June 2021 www.irjet.net p-ISSN: 2395-0072 © 2021, IRJET | Impact Factor value: 7.529 | ISO 9001:2008 Certified Journal | Page 2166 Smart LPG Gas Monitoring and Automatic Booking with Alert System Jayashree. N 1 , Dr. S. Kuzhalvaimozhi 2 1 PG Student, 2 Professor, Dept. of Information Science and Engineering, National Institute of Engineering, Mysuru, India.
- [13] Internet of Things based Hazardous Gas leakage Detection System using Arduino UNO Proceedings of the International Conference on Innovative Computing & Communication (ICICC) 2021 5 Pages Posted: 27 Apr 2021 Manasi Choche K.C.College of Engineering and Management Studies and Research Amuthavalli Yadav K.C.College of Engineering and Management Studies and Research Manjusha Shelke K.C.College of Engineering and Management Studies and Research Shobha Tyagi K.C.College of Engineering and Management Studies and Research Date Written: April 25, 2021
- [14] Arduino Based Gas Leakage Detection System Using IoT Mr. Inamdar. S. A1 , Pratiksha W2 , Smita W3 , Nikita H4 , Sonali W5 1Professor, Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering SVERI's College of Engineering, Pandharpur, Maharashtra, India 2,3,4,5Students, Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering SVERI's College of Engineering, Pandharpur, Maharashtra, India, © June 2021 | IJIRT | Volume 8 Issue 1 | ISSN: 2349-6002.
- [15] International Journal of Scientific Research & Engineering Trends Volume 6, Issue 3, May-June-2020, ISSN (Online): 2395-566X Gas Leakage Detection and Prevention using IOT Sanjoy Das, Sahana S, Soujanya K, Swathi M C Department of Computer Science and Engineering K S Institute of Technology Bengaluru, India sanjoydas@ksit.edu.in, sahana4606@gmail.com, soujanya.krishnamurti0181@gmail.com, swathi.chennakrishna@gmail.com.
- [16] International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET) e-ISSN: 2395-0056 Volume: 07 Issue: 04 | Apr 2020 www.irjet.net p-ISSN: 2395-0072 © 2020, IRJET | Impact Factor value: 7.34 | ISO 9001:2008 Certified Journal | Page 2378 IoT BASED GAS MONITORING SYSTEM USING ARDUINO GURU rama gayathri1, Yoga ananth2 1PG Scholar Dept of ECE, P.S.R. Engineering College, Sivakasi, Tamilnadu, India. 2Asst.profDept of ECE, P.S.R. Engineering College, Sivakasi, Tamilnadu, India.

- [17] International Research Journal of Advanced Engineering and Science ISSN (Online): 2455-9024 51 Ba Thanh Nguyen and Anh Vu Nguyen, "IoT Application for Gas Leakages Monitoring," International Research Journal of Advanced Engineering and Science, Volume 5, Issue 4, pp. 51-53, 2020. IoT Application for Gas Leakages Monitoring Ba Thanh Nguyen1 , Anh Vu Nguyen2 1, 2 Institute of Engineering and Technology, Thu Dau Mot University, Binh D.
- [18] IoT Gas Leakage Detector and Warning Generator Authors B. F. Alshammari Electrical Engineering Department, University of Hail, Saudi Arabia M. T. Chughtai Department of Electrical Engineering, College of Engineering, University of Hail, Saudi Arabia <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9847-6776> Volume: 10 | Issue: 4 | Pages: 6142-6146 | August 2020 | <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3712> Corresponding author: B. F. Alshammari.
- [19] IoT Based Gas Leakage Detection and Alarming System using Blynk platforms Noor Kareem Jumaa*, Younus Mohammed Abdulkhaleq, Muntadher Asaad Nadhim, Tariq Aziz Abbas Al-Mansour University College, Computer Technology Eng. Dept., Baghdad, Iraq. Received: 18 October 2021 Revised: 20 February 2022 Accepted: 22 February 2022 DOI: 10.37917/ijeee.18.1.8 Vol. 18| Issue 1| June 2022 This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. © 2022 The Authors. Published by Iraqi Journal for Electrical and Electronic Engineering by College of Engineering, University of Basrah. <https://doi.org/10.37917/ijeee.18.1.8> <https://www.ijeee.edu.iq> 64 Iraqi Journal for Electrical and Electronic Engineering.
- [20] Quest Journals Journal of Electronics and Communication Engineering Research Volume 8 ~ Issue 5 (2022) pp: 06-11 ISSN(Online) : 2321-5941 www.questjournals.org *Corresponding Author: Mr. Sivaprasad Lebaka 6 | Page Research Paper Gas Leakage Detection Using GSM Module & Arduino with SMS Alert Mr. Sivaprasad Lebaka, Associate Professor, Dept. of ECE, Siddhartha Institute of Science and Technology, Puttur, Andhra Pradesh, India.
- [15]. GAS LEAKAGE DETECTION AND MESSAGE ALERT SYSTEM BY Tasdid Hossain Id No: 161-15-7392 Sheikh Md. Kamrul Islam Rasel Id No: 161-15-7646 A.N.M. Mohaimen Id No: 161-15-7622 Ahmed Faisal Amit Id No: 161-15-7639 Supervised by Md. Sazzadur Ahamed Senior Lecturer Department of CSE Daffodil International University